

Vierkous — A concept for sustainable harbor redevelopment

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Figure 1 Overview Vierkous

The area Vierhavens (Four Harbors) in the port of Rotterdam is currently losing his function as a harbor. The objective of this project is to redevelop a mixed use area that is self-sufficient in food, water and energy. Vierkous is a symbiosis between existing pier and four new nature reserves. In 1912, the construction of the Vierhavens meant the ending of a lush tidal area: the Westkous.

Figure 2 Concept

In the new proposal, the old harbors will silt and four new estuaries will arise. This special nature reserves will supply the neighborhood of food and will clean their wastewater. Nutrient cycles are closed at the scale of the neighborhood. The hard concrete piers and soft estuaries create a sharp contrast between city and nature, but are inseparable and connected by a network of public spaces and buildings. This juxtaposition symbolizes the dependence between humanity and nature.

Figure 3 Artist impression of border between pier and estuary